

**RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ACHIEVEMENT-ORIENTED
LEADERSHIP STYLE AND TEACHERS' JOB SATISFACTION
IN NAKURU COUNTY, KENYA**

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Abstract:

This study investigated achievement leadership style practiced by head teachers' and job satisfaction of teachers'. The study was conducted among a random sample of 348 primary school teachers from Nakuru County, Kenya. A researcher developed questionnaire was administered and interview schedule. Correlation design was used for the study. Spearman's coefficient correlation analysis was used to predict relationships between variables however; they were subjected to hypotheses test. The objective of the study was to examine the relationship between head teachers' achievement-oriented leadership style and teachers' job satisfaction in primary schools. Teacher job satisfaction is influenced by head teacher who demonstrates ultimate goal achievement to teachers' through giving of challenging tasks and roles as well as creating confidence on followers. A conducive environment in school is vital for teachers who show lack of confidence in ability to complete a task and hence they need motivation in order for them to continue achieving towards the goals set. Moreover, achievement-oriented persons in leadership demonstrate that clear performance of high standards at work is vital and hence they show concern for subordinates' confidence. Although school tasks need to be set on clear guidelines and standards of performance, routine tasks need to be made more challenging and followers made aware to focus on high standards. An achievement-oriented leader should often seek for continuous improvement from the subordinates. Spearman rho correlation coefficient relationship between head teachers' achievement leadership style and teachers' job satisfaction was found to be significant. The study concluded that achievement oriented leadership style

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practice by head teachers' had a weak relationship although significant correlation to job satisfaction. In view of this foregoing teachers' work need to be made more challenging and interesting to eliminate routine activities. The study recommended that schools should continue focusing on leadership practices as part of their professional learning and leadership development. This development enables to maintain a continuous supply of future leaders and sustainable leadership. Institutional heads need to learn more about human behavior as it impacts on teacher performance. Head teachers' through their actions and attitudes should create an enabling environment which induces motivation on teachers towards achievement of desired goals.

Keywords: achievement-oriented leadership, job satisfaction, leadership, work relationship

1. Introduction

1.1 Achievement-oriented leadership style and job satisfaction

Job satisfaction has been frequently examined topic in education and management and considered an indicator to evaluate educational attainments of school effectiveness (Joo, 2011). Achievement-oriented leadership sets clear and challenging goals for subordinates however, the achievement oriented leader challenges the followers to perform their best and demonstrates a high degree of confidence in their abilities to do the job (Mat, 2008; Jones & Geroge, 2011). The leader establishes a high standard of excellence for subordinates and seeks continuous improvement further; leader shows a high degree of confidence in subordinates (Northouse, 2013). In view of this foregoing, some leaders may claim to challenge subordinates to perform their work at the highest possible level but followers have minimal continuous improvement. In addition to expecting that challenging goals and standards must be met, Achievement-Oriented leaders believe in subordinates' capabilities (Jones & George, 2011; Northouse, 2010). In contrary, this is partial because of distrust between followers and leader in school environment.

Achievement-Oriented leadership is appropriate when followers are open to autocratic leadership, have external locus of control, and follower's ability is high; when task is simple, authority is strong, and job satisfaction from co-workers is either high or low (Lussier & Achua, 2010). This is corroborated in research study that leadership is the ability to influence a group towards the achievement of a vision or set of goals (Robbins *et al.*, 2010). Similarly, Daft (2005) contended that leadership behavior should clarify goals and set performance standards to be achieved. Nevertheless, this study argues that achievement oriented leadership may achieve performance through recognizing, encouraging and delegating task to followers. The study largely concurs with observations made by Davis, Darling-Hammond, LaPointe, & Meyerson (2005) that the growing consensus on the attributes of effective head teachers show that successful school leaders influence achievement through the support and development of effective teachers and the implementation of effective organizational processes.

Negron (2008) noted achievement-oriented style is suited for unclear tasks and subordinates who may need a morale booster to increase their confidence in ability to accomplish the given goal. Achievement oriented style is effective when work is complex and the environment uncertain. This is because it can increase subordinates' self confidence that they are able to attain the goals. The achievement oriented leader tries to change attitudes of employees so as to seek continuous improvement (Leana, 2013). However, achievement oriented leadership on the other hand is predicted to increase the follower effort and satisfaction when the task is unstructured and complex by increasing the follower self-confidence and the expectation of successfully accomplishing a challenging task or goal. This is explained in the concepts of the Path-Goal Theory where environment and the staff factors are moderators in leadership style and staff performance relationship as well as in leadership style and job satisfaction relationship (Northouse, 2013).

According to path goal theory, for leaders to be effective, they need to: recognize the needs of those they lead and try to satisfy these needs through the workplace, reward people for achieving their goals, help subordinates identify the most effective paths they need to take to reach their goals (Northouse, 2013). This concur with assertion made by (Yukl, 2010) that achievement oriented style takes a transactional approach, which specifies expectations, clarify responsibilities, provides recognition and rewards to attain the desired performance. Various studies suggest that leader reward behaviors are predictors of subordinates performance and satisfaction. The meta-analysis conducted by Podsakoff, Bommer, & MacKenzie (2006) suggested that leader behaviors are positively related to subordinate job satisfaction.

As Path-goal theory focused on how leaders influence followers' expectations Robert House, the originator of the theory, proposed a model in which leader behavior is acceptable when employees regard it as a source of satisfaction (Kreitner & Kinicki, 1995). In addition to this, leader behavior is motivational when it eliminates factors that hinder goal accomplishment but provides emotional support to the employees, and grants meaningful recognition in return for success. House claimed that the leader should stay on the right path to achieve challenging goals since achievement- oriented leadership is setting high standards and challenging goals for the employees by encouraging them to perform at their highest level (Northouse, 2013). Drawing from these suggestions, teachers' academic qualifications are successes thus need to be recognized as part of achievement in the right path towards exhibiting goal attainment.

According to Portin, Paul, Michael, and Lauren (cited in Maina, 2014) the core mandate of the head teacher's job is to diagnose his or her particular school's needs and to meet these needs by utilizing the resources and talents available. This is because achievement oriented leadership agitate for performance (Mat, 2008 & Yukl, 2010). Portin *et al.*, further assert that regardless of school type, schools need leadership critical in area of human resource for example; inducting, mentoring teachers and administrators; developing leadership capacity and professional development opportunities. Nevertheless, according to an OECD report (Schleicher, 2012) more countries around the world require improved achievement from their schools. It is

therefore imperative to have teachers' professional development granted so as to continuously achieve greater goals in schools as well as filling the gap needed to initiate supported mentorship and internship to teachers.

To this end leader reward behaviors are predictors of teacher performance and satisfaction, therefore the meta-analysis conducted by Podsakoff, Boomer, & Mackenzie (2006) affirms that leader behaviors are positively related to subordinate job satisfaction. This develops quality of teachers' work and encourages them to contribute more (Hars & Ou, 2002). Behaviors by the head teacher indicate personal achievement satisfaction positively affect motivation to the extent that the teachers themselves have high needs for achievement. Malik (2013) reveal that achievement-oriented leader behaviors have significant relationship with supervision and job in general and also significantly related with the co-worker and work.

2. Objective

To determine relationship between head teachers' achievement-oriented leadership style and teachers' job satisfaction in primary schools, Nakuru County.

3. Theoretical framework

The study used theory of leadership to investigate relationship of head teachers' achievement leadership style and job satisfaction therefore, the study employed path-goal leadership theory developed by House (cited in Martin, 2012) and argued the theory is based on how leaders facilitate task performance to subordinates which help achieve rewards because employees are motivated, recognized, and satisfied hence; its relevant to the study. Robbins (2005) believed that path-goal theory is the most influential contingency approach to leadership. However, Richard *et al.*, 2012 (cited in Malik 2013) believe path-goal theory is the most sophisticated and comprehensive contingency theory. According to Path-Goal theory, leader provides necessary direction and support to subordinates to achieve individual as well as organizational goals (Silverthorne, 2001).

4. Methodology

To determine the degree of relationship between achievement-oriented leadership style and teacher job satisfaction the study adopted a correlational research design. Cresswell (2012); Gall and Borg (2007) described correlational study as appropriate design to discover relationship between variables by using correlational statistics. Questionnaires were used to collect data from the population in order to determine current conditions with respect to one or more variables. The study targeted 602 head teachers' and 7003 teachers in Nakuru County. However, the study population was 240 and 3700 for head teachers' and teachers' respectively from 4 sub counties. Cluster random sampling was used to select sub counties. The Sub Counties had similar settings of rural and urban

representation. Researcher employed proportionate sampling to select 148 schools from sampled sub counties. Head teachers' were automatically drawn from sampled schools. Sample size for teachers were selected through stratified sampling thus 148 males and 200 females from upper primary made a sample of 348 with simple random sampling being adopted to select teachers in the individual schools. Curriculum Support Officers were purposively selected and interviewed to shed more light. The study used formula recommended by Krejcie and Morgan (cited in Gall and Borg, 2007 Saowanee, Wallapha & Tang 2014) to determine the sample size. Statistical Package of Social Sciences program was used to manage in data entry and presentation of scores. Spearman's rho correlation statistics analysis was carried out to establish relationship between achievement-oriented leadership style and teachers job satisfaction. To achieve correlation, positive *rho* meant that higher ranks on one variable were associated with higher ranks on the other variable and larger absolute values of *rho* indicated a stronger relationship between the variables (Harris, 1998). Hypothesis- t test was conducted to determine the significant level.

5. Results and discussion

5.1 Partial correlation between achievement leadership style and teachers job satisfaction

The study on relationship between head teachers' leadership styles and teachers' job satisfaction is critical hence analysis to find out relationship between variables. Partial correlation was carried out in all the four objectives of the study. Kothari (2011) pointed out that partial correlation aims at measuring the relation between a dependent variable and a particular independent variable by holding all other variables constant. Each partial coefficient correlation of leadership style is to measure the effect of its independent variable on the dependent variable. The summary of analysis is structured as per research questions.

Table 1 shows achievement leadership style in relationship to control variables, directive style, supportive style, participative style and job satisfaction held constant.

Table 1: Partial Correlation on Job Satisfaction to Achievement Leadership Style

Control variables	Achievement		
Directive, Supportive, & Participative	Job	Correlation	.192
	Satisfaction	Significance (2-tailed)	.001
		Df	300

Table 1 indicates a partial correlation of 0.192 and a degree of freedom of 300 on achievement leadership style thus confirming the results obtained in spearman's rho coefficient analysis appropriate.

5.2 Relationship on achievement oriented leadership and teachers' job satisfaction

Research question

How does head teachers' achievement oriented leadership style relate to teachers' job satisfaction in primary schools? The mean of the achievement leadership style and Job satisfaction were obtained by taking the average of the teacher responses to all the questions under this leadership style and job satisfaction for each of the respondent. Spearman Rank correlation coefficient was then computed and preferred since the original data was based on ranks. A total of 305 questionnaires responses were analyzed to derive the Spearman *rho*. The results of the findings are summarizes in Table 2.

Table 2: Relationship between Achievement Oriented Leadership and Teachers Job Satisfaction

Spearman's rho	Correlation Coefficient	Job Satisfaction	Achievement Oriented
	N	305	0.445**

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

A Spearman *rho* correlation coefficient of 0.445** was found. Analysis indicates that there is a significant relationship between head teachers' achievement oriented leadership style and teachers job satisfaction. Spearman *rho* correlation coefficient calculated established positive correlation ($rho(305) = 0.445, p < 0.05$), indicating a significant relationship between the two variables. As head teachers demonstrated achievement leadership style, teachers in schools tend to have higher satisfaction toward job in the organization.

Mat (2008) affirms that there is significant linear relationship between leadership styles and staff job satisfaction moreover, the beta weights showed that the achievement oriented style of leadership (0.251) is relatively stronger. This alludes that achievement leadership style of 0.445 found in this study is a predictor for teachers' job satisfaction. The results presented may indicate that head teachers' got more concerned on importance of teachers' needs and skills rather than the school's goals achievements. This might have made the young teachers to be more satisfied on the job than the old folk. The increase in levels of job satisfaction on achievement oriented leadership could have been contributed by confidence of head teacher in giving challenging tasks to teachers. The association between variables is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Achievement Oriented Leadership Style and Teachers Job Satisfaction

The scatter in Figure 1 shows a positive correlation between leadership style and job satisfaction for both head teachers and teachers. This is indication that head teachers' assigned challenging goals to teachers. Similarly, head teachers' demonstrated confidence in teachers. This study established majority of teachers (149) appreciated head teachers' had confidence in them and they were given challenging goals. However, report from field officers showed head teachers' gave challenging tasks in order to avoid inferiority from teachers (CSO, 2015).

Negron (2008) noted achievement-oriented style is suited for unclear tasks and subordinates who may need a morale booster to increase their confidence in ability to accomplish the given goal. The achievement oriented leadership attempts to change attitudes of employees so as to seek continuous improvement (Leana, 2013). Northhouse (2013) asserted achievement-oriented leadership sets clear and challenging goals for subordinates nevertheless, Lussier & Achua (2010) found out that achievement-Oriented leadership was appropriate when followers are open to autocratic leadership, had external locus of control, and follower's ability was high hence tasks completion therefore head teachers' in schools made clear and challenging goals.

The findings in this current study allude achievement-oriented leadership style positively encourages teachers' recognition hence increases job satisfaction moderated by the need for achievement. Finally, an achievement oriented style is deemed effective among head teachers where the work is complex and the environment uncertain because it increases teachers' self-confidence to attain the goals (Martin, 2012). As head teachers demonstrate achievement oriented style, teachers become more satisfied. Co-efficient determination of (0.445^2) ; was found accounting to 19.80% of teachers' job satisfaction was due to the head teacher demonstrating achievement oriented leadership style.

5.3 Hypotheses test on achievement oriented leadership and job satisfaction

The correlation was subjected to hypothesis test using the matched-pairs with t-test procedure. The analysis was done to see whether there was statistically significant true difference between the values of achievement oriented leadership and job satisfaction.

H₀₁: There is statistically significance relationship between achievement oriented leadership and teacher job satisfaction.

H₁₁: There is no statistically significance relationship between achievement oriented leadership and teacher job satisfaction.

The calculated value of t was – 12.945 at significance level of 95% , 2 tailed with 304 degree of freedom. The p-value was 0.0000 and since it was less than 0.05 the null hypothesis was rejected. From this it can be inferred that there was no relationship between achievement leadership style and job satisfaction.

6. Conclusions

Achievement-oriented leadership style practiced by head teachers' had a positive significant relationship evidenced by high value to job satisfaction. Teachers also expressed head teachers had confidence with the effort they put towards task and gave challenging roles however, teachers were opposed to achievement style. The study therefore concluded that teacher morale needed to be boosted, recognized and clear goals set for improvement.

6.1 Recommendations

The study recommends that schools should continue focusing on leadership practices as part of their professional learning and leadership development. Institutional heads need to learn more about human behavior as it impacts on teacher performance. Head teachers' through their actions and attitudes should create environment which induces motivation on teachers.

The study recommends introduction of policy on formalized recognized structures for improved work conditions such as creation of teacher professional association, departments, subject heads that benefit expanded structure in an effort to increase teachers' job satisfaction.

Knowing the importance of leadership styles, by means of this study, would provide additional evidence to Teachers employer and the Ministry of Education Science and Technology in training head teachers with effective job-embedded support structures, such as internships, mentorship programs with trained experienced mentors and expert group, proficiency coaching, and performance evaluation. These ensure effective professional competence for novice head teachers during their formative years. Head teachers can be informed difference between leadership and management.

Availing a policy on radical reforms in developing leadership framework that prepare teachers for leadership ranks is vital. Policy should be collaborated with teacher training institutions, universities and Curriculum Developers. The policy framework

need to incorporate professional association for teachers with responsibility of ensuring practicing teachers are well prepared, regularly monitored.

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